

FOCUS ON ORAL SPEECH IN TEACHING FRENCH

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Abstract. This article examines the importance of discourse in teaching French as a foreign language, emphasizing a communicative and cognitive approach. It explores the benefits of learning through speaking, the challenges students face, and provides effective teaching strategies to promote speaking. The article emphasizes the importance of creating a stimulating learning environment and implementing interesting activities that encourage active student participation.

Key words: French as a foreign language, oral education, communicative, cognitive approach, development of oral speech, teaching strategies.

ФОКУС НА УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ФРАНЦУЗСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение дискурса в преподавании французского языка как иностранного, уделяя особое внимание коммуникативному и когнитивному подходу. В нем исследуются преимущества обучения через говорение, проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся, и предлагаются эффективные стратегии обучения, способствующие развитию говорения. В статье подчеркивается важность создания стимулирующей среды обучения и реализации интересных мероприятий, стимулирующих активное участие учащихся.

Ключевые слова: французский язык как иностранный, устное обучение, коммуникативный, когнитивный подход, развитие устной речи, стратегии обучения.

Enter. One of the main ways to communicate in a foreign language is through speaking skills. Learning to speak a foreign language is an important factor because speech is the main form of communication and a person who has good speaking skills can communicate effectively with others. Therefore, teaching communicative language involves performing certain language functions or tasks: greeting, introducing yourself, expressing your likes and dislikes, or asking someone about their hobbies and interests, while in a row, summarizes how you can find directions to a place. These are actually very specific things related to language. Language came into existence as a means of communication. It exists and is alive only through speech. When we talk about teaching a foreign language, we must first teach it as a means of communication. Speaking is one of the four skills that is important. It is a skill that the language learner will greatly appreciate in unexpected encounters in real life. At the same time, it is undoubtedly true that a confident speaker cannot communicate without the other three skills. Therefore, the four skills (reading, speaking, listening and writing) must be included and interconnected within the framework of French language teaching. Many methods and techniques can be used to develop students' speaking skills. Each style has its own advantages and disadvantages. It really depends on the skill of the teacher, he should adapt and choose the right methods depending on the subject, the age, abilities, and characteristics of the students¹.

¹<https://bestpublication.org/index.php/sit/article/download/6947/7270>

Analysis and results. There are several types of using conversations in the auditorium: Dialogic speech - in which students talk to each other through a creative approach. In the modern French language teaching methodology, the use of dialogues is effective primarily for the development of speaking skills. These skills can be taught through a variety of teaching aids, including literary texts. Such interactions avoid the traditional memorization and monotony of texts and turn them into lively French discourse. It also helps students to increase their vocabulary and improve their memory. During dialogues, students practice fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. The student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. The learning process is conducted interactively. They can use short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek and French writers to create vocabulary, prepare, organize and present literary interpretations. Students can improve their speaking skills through listening comprehension. Receptive form of auditory-speech activity.

Interpretation of speech during listening is mainly based on auditory sensations. During listening, students pay attention to the tone of the spoken words, and through repetition, these words are consolidated in memory. In the process of starting a conversation in French, the dialogues heard as an experiment help the student and form his skills. Learning French by watching short and educational films ².

Nowadays, teachers are taking into account the demands of students to watch real movies along with reading books, magazines and newspapers. It is known that not only printed materials can serve as a great source of learning, but also songs and movies play an important role in learning foreign languages. The importance of teaching vocabulary. Vocabulary is the main part of language learning. In addition to learning new vocabulary, the student can deal with unfamiliar vocabulary while listening or reading a text, overcome vocabulary gaps in speech and writing, and make good use of certain phrases. and must use strategies to learn new words.

Forms of working with computer educational programs in foreign language classes include: vocabulary learning; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical phenomena. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information: regional geographical materials, youth life news, articles in newspapers and magazines, etc. can be solved: building reading skills and powers to use global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn French. In addition, this work is aimed at studying the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand the worldview of schoolchildren, to establish and maintain business relations and relations with their peers in French-speaking countries ³. Students participate in online tests, quizzes, contests, olympiads, correspondence with peers in other countries, conversations, video conferences, etc.

The teaching of French as a foreign language (FLE) has developed significantly in recent decades, moving from a grammatical and lexical approach to a more communicative and cognitive approach. This development can be explained by the increasing importance of speech in language

²<https://moluch.ru/archive/396/87618/>

³<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/modern-methods-of-learning-French-language-and-other-foreign-languages>

learning. Speaking is the basis of intercultural communication and enables students to integrate into a French-speaking environment and participate actively in society. Learning through speaking has many advantages for FLE learners. First of all, it helps to develop self-confidence and overcome the fear of speaking. Regular speaking practice ensures fluency and spontaneity in oral expression. In addition, speaking helps to remember vocabulary and grammatical structures, as well as to understand pronunciation and intonation. Finally, learning through discourse allows students to develop interpersonal relationships and make connections with other people.

Summary. This article explores the important role of speaking French as a foreign language and emphasizes the importance of a communicative and cognitive approach. The benefits of learning through speaking are undeniable, it builds fluency, confidence, vocabulary acquisition and cultural understanding. However, students often suffer from fear of making mistakes, limited vocabulary, and difficulty generating ideas. Pedagogical strategies that encourage active participation and create a safe and supportive learning environment are essential to address these challenges.

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